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CHEWABLE TABLETS: NO WATER ORAL ADMINISTRATION

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ABSTRACT

Chewable tablets which are required to be broken and chewed in between the teeth before ingestion. These tablets are given to the children who have difficulty in swallowing and to the adults who dislike swallowing. These tablets are intended to disintegrate smoothly in the mouth at a moderate rate either with or without actual chewing, characteristically chewable tablets have a smooth texture upon disintegration, are pleasant tasting and leave no bitter or unpleasant taste. Geriatric and pediatric patients and travelling patients who may not have ready access to water are most need of easy swallowing dosage forms like chewable tablets. The composition of chewable tablet consists of gum core, which may or may not be coated. The core is composed of an insoluble gum base like fillers, waxes, antioxidants, sweeteners, flavoring agents. The present review focuses on formulation, method of manufacture and evaluation of chewable tablets.

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INTRODUCTION

Chewable tablets which are required to be broken and chewed in between the teeth before ingestion. These tablets are given to the children who have difficulty in swallowing and to the adults who dislike swallowing. ^[1] These tablets are intended to disintegrate smoothly in mouth at a moderate rate either with or without actual chewing, characteristically chewable tablets have a smooth texture upon disintegration, are pleasant tasting and leave no bitter or unpleasant taste. Successful tablet formulation development involves the careful selection of ingredients in order to manufacture a robust solid dosage form. Choosing the appropriate excipient to perform a specific function in a tablet formulation such as disintegration or lubrication can be critical to achieving acceptable manufacturing performance. Sweeteners, both naturally occurring and synthetic are one type of functional excipient commonly used in chewable tablet formulations to mask the unpleasant tastes and facilitate pediatric dosing. Ideally upon chewing, they are broken down in the mouth and release their ingredients in the process and therefore, do not have much lag time as required for the disintegration of tablets before absorption from stomach. Chewable tablet are often employed when the active ingredient is intended to act in a localized manner rather than systemically. Chewable tablet is one that is palatable and may be chewed and ingested with little or no water. Manufacturing of chewable tablet is generally done using either wet granulation process or direct compression. Increasingly, micronized and submicron forms of therapeutically and physiologically active substances are incorporated into tablet formulation to take advantage of the enhanced absorption characteristics of these forms. They are also used in the administration of antacids and carminatives. Mannitol is widely used as an excipient in chewable tablet for its non-hygroscopic nature for moisture sensitive drugs. As we know difficulty in swallowing (Dysphasia) is common among all age groups, especially in elderly and in also seen of swallowing of conventional tablets and capsules. Geriatric and pediatric patients and travelling patients who may not have ready access to water are most need of easy swallowing dosage forms like chewable tablets. The composition of chewable tablet consists of gum core, which may or may not be coated. The core is composed of an insoluble gum base like fillers, waxes, antioxidants, sweeteners, flavouring agents. The percentage of gum base varies from 30-60% depending upon the base used and its properties. A flavouring agent is included to make it more palatable.

Chewable Tablets:

Definition^[2]:

- Chewable tablets are the tablets which are required to be broken and chewed in between the teeth before ingestion. These are usually given to the children who have difficulty in swallowing and to the adults who dislike swallowing.
- Chewable tablets are preferred for the drugs having high dose, the tablets of which cannot be swallowed.
- Sweeteners are one type of functional excipient commonly used in chewable tablet formulations to mask the unpleasant tastes and facilitate pediatric dosing ^[3].
- Ideally chewable formulations must have smooth texture upon disintegration, pleasant taste and no bitter or unpleasant after taste. Upon chewing, they are broken down in the mouth and release their ingredients in the process and therefore, do not have much lag time as required for the disintegration of tablets before absorption from stomach ^[4].
- Chewable tablets are often employed when active ingredient is intended to act in a localized manner rather than systemically ^[5].
- Chewable tablet is one that is palatable and may be chewed and ingested with little or no water ^[6].

Advantages^[7,8]:

The advantages of chewable tablets include

1. They provide quick and complete disintegration of the tablet and thus obtain a rapid drug effect after swallowing and dissolution.
2. Easy administration especially for children and elderly people.
3. Could be administered when water is not available.

Disadvantages^[9]:

The disadvantages of chewable tablet include

1. They cost more than the usual tablet or capsule.
2. They have less potency than a tablet or capsule.

Potential Candidates for Chewable Tablets^[10]:

Category	Examples
Antacids	Magnesium Carbonate Magnesium oxide Aluminium oxide Aluminium Hydroxide Magnesium hydroxide Magnesium silicate/ trisilicate Magnesium Aluminium trisilicate
Carminatives	Simethicone
Paediatric vitamins	Vitamin D ₃
Antihistamines	Cetirizine hydrochloride Loratidine Chlorpheniramine maleate
Antimotility agents	Loperamide Bismuth subsalicylate
Antiepileptic agents	Lamotrigine Carbamazepine
Antibiotics	Amoxicillin Clavulunate potassium Roxithromycin
Anthelminthics	Albendazole Mebendazole Niclosamide Levamisole
Antiasthmatic agents	Montelukast sodium
Analgesics	Aspirin Acetaminophen Ibuprofen
Non Steroidal Anti Inflammatory Drugs	Diclofenac sodium Etodolac

Excipients that are used in the formulation of chewable tablets:**Diluents^[11]:**

- ❖ Diluents provide the required bulk of the tablet when the drug dosage itself is inadequate to produce tablets of adequate weight and size.
- ❖ Usually the range of diluent may vary from 5-80%.
- ❖ Diluents are often added to tablet formulations for secondary reasons like to provide better tablet properties such as:
 - i. To provide improved cohesion
 - ii. To allow direct compression manufacturing
 - iii. To enhance flow
 - iv. To adjust weight of tablet as per die capacity

Ex:

- Mannitol
- Xylitol
- Sucrose
- Lactose
- Sorbitol

Mannitol:

It is widely used in chewable tablets because of its negative heat of solution. Its slow solubility and its mild cooling sensation in mouth.

Two hydrolyzed starches Emdex and Celutab, which are basically 90-92% dextrose and about 3 to 5% maltose. They are free flowing and directly compressible. These materials may be used in place of mannitol in chewable tablets because of their sweetness and smooth feeling in the mouth.

Some of the sucrose based diluents such as Sugartab (90 to 93% sucrose plus 7 to 10% invert sugar), DiPac (97% sucrose plus 3% modified dextrans) and Nu Tab (95% sucrose and 4% invert sugar with a small amount of corn starch and Magnesium stearate are employed with or without mannitol in chewable tablets.

Binders ^[11]:

- ❖ They impart cohesiveness to the tablet formulation that ensures the tablet remaining intact after compression.

Ex:

- Starch,
- Gelatin,
- Acacia,
- Sodium alginate
- Hydroxy ethyl cellulose
- Hydroxy propyl cellulose

Superdisintegrants ^[11]:

- ❖ These are the agents that are added to the tablet to promote the breakup of the tablet into smaller fragments in an aqueous environment thereby increasing available surface area and promoting more rapid release of the drug substance.
- ❖ They promote moisture penetration and dispersion of the tablet matrix ^[12,13].

Ex:

- Crospovidone,
- Croscarmellose sodium,
- Microcrystalline cellulose,
- Sodium starch glycolate

Lubricants ^[11]:

- ❖ Lubricants are the agents that act by reducing friction by interposing an intermediate layer between the tablet constituents and the die wall during compression and ejection.

Ex:

Insoluble lubricants:

1. Stearates (Magnesium stearate, Calcium stearate, Sodium stearate) 0.25-1%
2. Talc 1-2%

Water soluble lubricants:

1. Boric acid 1% w/w
2. Sodium benzoate 5% w/w

Glidants ^[11]:

- ❖ Glidants are added to the formulation to improve the flow properties of the material which is to be fed into the die cavity and aid in particle rearrangement within the die during the early stages of compression.

Ex:

- Colloidal silica such as syloid, Cab-O-Sil or Aerosil (0.25 to 3%) Sodium silicoaluminate (0.75%)
- Talc (5%)
- Corn starch (5 to 10%).

Flavours ^[11]:

- ❖ Flavors are commonly used to improve the taste of chewable tablets. Flavors are incorporated either as solids (spray dried flavors) or oils or aqueous (water soluble) flavors.
- ❖ Solids (dry flavors) are easier to handle and generally more stable than oils.
- ❖ Oil is usually added at the lubrication step because of its sensitivity to moisture and their tendency to volatilize when heated during drying. It may also be adsorbed onto an excipient and added during the lubrication process.
- ❖ The maximum amount of oil that can be added to granulation without affecting tableting characteristics is 0.5 to 0.75 % w/w. aqueous flavors are less used because of its instability on aging.

Ex:

- Citric acid flavor,
- Grape flavor,
- Raspberry flavor,
- Lemon flavor and
- Cherry flavors

Sweeteners ^[11]:

❖ Sweeteners are added primarily to chewable tablets to exclude or limit the use of sugar in tablets.

Ex:**Natural sweeteners:**

- Mannitol,
- Lactose,
- Sucrose,
- Dextrose

Artificial sweeteners:

- Saccharin,
- Cyclamate,
- Aspartame

Manufacturing of Chewable Tablets:

For chewable tablets, manufacturing means proper incorporation of the colouring agent, maintenance of correct moisture content, and achievement of proper tablet hardness. All of these are the routine responsibility of the manufacturer in the department once the parameters have been established during development. The process development and scale up considerations be thoroughly studied in order to ensure the establishment of proper specifications. If colour is added as a lake for direct compression blend, then the blending operation consists of the addition of coloured powder to white granules. So, coloured powder will uniformly coat the white granules. However, during compression, the granules release fresh white material to the surface, resulting in white spots on a coloured background or “speckling”.

Methods of Manufacturing:

The Chewable tablets were prepared by using the following methods:

1. Non aqueous Granulation/Dry granulation
2. Aqueous Granulation/Wet granulation
3. Direct compression

Granulation:

Granulation is the process in which primary powder particles are made to adhere to form larger, multi-particles entities called granules. Pharmaceutically granules have size range between 0.2 to 4.0 mm. Granulation is used to improve flow and compressibility of powders and to prevent segregation of the blend components. Granulation is mainly done by using two techniques. Dry granulation is the novel method for semi-automatic production of granules. The method is applicable to any solid dosage pharmaceutical products. Dry granulation method replaces existing solid dosage form development and manufacturing. technologies offering more rapid development and better quality. In this process, the powder mixture is compressed without the use of heat and solvent. Two methods are used for dry granulation. The more widely used is slugging where the powder is recompressed and the resulting tablet are milled to yield the granules.

Wet granulation

Wet granulation is the most commonly used granulation method. This process involves wet massing of powder blend with a granulating liquid, wet sizing and drying. The granulating liquid contains a solvent which must be volatile so that it can be removed by drying and must be non-toxic in nature. Typical liquid include water, ethanol and Isopropyl alcohol. In the traditional wet granulation method the wet mass is forced through a sieve to produce wet granules which are subsequently dried.

Direct Compression

Direct compression is the most popular choice because it provides the shortest, most effective and least complex way to produce tablets. This method is mainly used when a group of ingredients can be blended. This is more suitable for moisture and heat sensitive API's since it eliminates wetting and drying steps and increase the stability of active ingredient by reducing detrimental (harmful) effects. In this process, API mixed with the excipients and lubricant, followed by compression which makes the product easy to process.

Evaluation Parameters for Chewable Tablets:

The variety of evaluation parameters must be kept in mind during the formulation of chewable tablets. These are given as follows:

In-process Organoleptic evaluation

This evaluation takes place at various stages in the development of a chewable tablet. These are as follows:

1. Evaluation of drug itself: It involves characterization and comparison of the substance in an absolute amount or against a known reference standard.
2. Evaluation of coated drug: It involves comparison against the pure drug as well as different coating treatment.
3. Evaluation of unflavoured baseline formulation: It involves comparison among different vehicles, proportion of vehicles or other formulation variables in presence of coated drug.
4. Evaluation of flavoured baseline formulation: It involves comparison among different flavoured formulations.
5. Evaluation of final selection and product acceptance test: It involves comparison between two formulations or competitive product.

Chemical Evaluation

It involves the following:

1. Assay of drug content
2. Dosage uniformity
3. *In vitro* and *In vivo* Evaluation

Physical Evaluation

It involves the following:

1. Tablet physical appearance
2. Hardness
3. Friability
4. Disintegration
5. Dissolution

CONCLUSION

Chewable tablet can release an active substance at a controlled rate over an extended period of time providing a prolonged local effect. They are used in the successful treatment of minor pains, headaches, pains of cold, muscular aches, etc. requires rapid absorption of therapeutic doses of the active substance.

Chewable tablet as a drug delivery system could be beneficial in minor pain treatment, when buccal absorption results in fast onset of action and reduces the risk of gastrointestinal side effects. Chewable tablet provides benefits to systemic drug delivery, especially if the active substance is absorbed through the buccal mucosa. Chewing gum formulations containing nicotine, lobeline and silver acetate have been clinically tested as aids to smoking cessation. Several chewing gum formulations containing caffeine, guarana or chromium are available. Caffeine and guarana are central stimulating anorectic agents that have proved to increase the metabolic rate.

Table 1: Recent Literature on Chewable Tablets.

S. No	Drug name	Category	Reason for development into chewable tablet	Technology	Excipients used in the formulation	Result	Reference
1.	Albendazole	Anthelmintic	Geriatric and paediatric patients have difficulty in swallowing tablets. So to avoid this problem, it is formulated as chewable tablet	Non aqueous granulation, Aqueous granulation, Direct compression	Lactose, Starch, Sodium glycolate, Isopropyl alcohol, Mannitol, Sodium sachharin, Carmofine color, Pineapple flavor, Magnesium stearate, Talc, Aerosil	The tablets prepared by direct compression showed better dissolution rate than tablets prepared by non aqueous granulation and aqueous granulation	14
2.	Loperamide	Antidiarrhoeal	To avoid difficulty in swallowing	Wet granulation	Simethicone, Microcrystalline cellulose (Avicel ph – 102), Lactose monohydrate, Lactose DCL – 21, Povidone K-30[PVP K-30], Croscarmellose sodium(Premillose), Crospovidone XL-10, Sodium lauryl	Use of simethicone to dry powder blend improved hardness and provided good physical appearance to the tablets. Addition of Loperamide hydrochloride to binder solution and use of proper amount of surfactant (SLS) to	15

					sulphate, Hydroxy propyl cellulose, colors(Rohadine), flavors(Givaudan), Aspartame, Colloidal silica, Magnesium stearate, Simethicone	blend increased blend uniformity and better dissolution of Loperamide hydrochloride	
3.	Loratidine	Histamine H1 receptor antagonist	It is difficult for children to swallow tablet, so to avoid this it is formulated into chewable tablet	Wet granulation	Microcrystalline cellulose, Guar gum, Lactose monohydrate, Mannitol, Ethyl cellulose, Maize starch, Povidone K 30, D&C Yellow No.6, Citric acid, Raspberry flavor, Aspartame, Sodium starch glycolate, Colloidal silica, Magnesium stearate	Loratidine formulated by using Avicel CE 15 and starch paste showed better physical character of chewable tablets and better dissolution profile when compared to the innovator.	16
4.	Mebendazole	Anthelmintic	It is bitter in taste and difficult to swallow hence it is formulated as chewable tablet	Wet granulation	Lactose, Mannitol, Sodium starch glycolate, Magnesium stearate, Sodium sachharin, Vanilla	The tablet containing lactose and sodium starch glycolate (1.6% w/w) is the best chewable tablet with minimum disintegration time, sufficient hardness, pleasant taste and meeting all USP limits	17
5.	Etodolac	Non steroidal anti inflammatory drug	For increase in etodolac solubility at pH of buccal cavity and ease in administration	Coevaporation technique	Sodium lauryl sulphate, Mannitol, Ethanol, Methanol, Sodium stearyl fumarate, Sodium bicarbonate, Microcrystalline cellulose, Aspartame, Strawberry flavor, Galen, Emedex	Etodolac chewable tablets met USP monograph for Etodolac tablets, with 86% dissolved amount within 15min	18
6.	Guava extract	Anticariogenic	To mask the bitter taste and unpleasant mouth feel and for local action it is formulated as chewable tablet.	Wet granulation	Poly vinyl pyrrolidone K 30 (10% solution), Mannitol, Aerosil, Magnesium stearate, Peppermint flavor, Menthol	The 32 MIC tablet (160mg of guava extract) had highest growth inhibitory effect against Streptococcus mutans.	19
7.	Lamotrigine	Antiepileptic	It is bitter drug, slightly soluble in water. So to mask the taste it is formulated as chewable tablet by complexation with Precirol ATO-05	Melt granulation	Crospovidone, Sodium starch glycolate, Precirol ATO-05, Pearlitol D 200, Aspartame, Sodium chloride, Mint flavor, Peppermint flavor, Tween 80, Cherry flavor, Aerosil,	Taste masking of Lamotrigine by preparing taste masked granules of Lamotrigine with Precirol ATO-05 showed good taste and these tablets are useful for paediatric and geriatric patients	20

8.	Levamisole	Anthelmintic	Because of difficulty in swallowing it is formulated as chewable tablet	Wet granulation	Magnesium stearate, Stearic acid, Eudragit EPO Sodium lauryl sulphate, Polyvinyl pyrrolidone, Lactose, Mannitol, Sodium starch glycolate, Magnesium stearate, Stearic acid, Starch, Vanilla flavor, Sodium saccharin	and can be commercialized	Tablets containing 21
9.	Ibuprofen, Paracetamol	Non steroidal anti-inflammatory drug	Because of bitter taste and poor water solubility these are formulated as chewable tablets	Ion exchange technique	Mannitol, Ethyl cellulose, Magnesium stearate, Methyl cellulose, Avicel PH 101, Povidone K 90, Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose, Strawberry flavor, Orange flavor, Vanilla flavor	Results showed that ion exchange complexation with indion 204 resins could efficiently mask Paracetamol and Ibuprofen bitter taste when compared with the commonly used taste masking techniques and showed excellent results regarding powder flow and tableting properties	22
10.	Acetaminophen	Analgesic, Antipyretic	To suppress bitterness it is formulated as chewable tablet	Melt granulation	Witepsol [®] (R) H-15,W-35,S-55,E-75,E-85 and Witocan [®] (R) H & 42/44, Sucrose, Xylitol, Sacharin, Aspartame,Sucralose,Benecoat BMI-40 or Coca powder	Witocan H tablet with Sc1 –B5 is suggested as the best Acetaminophen chewable tablet exhibiting suppressed bitterness, low sweetness, improved oral feeling and good drug release	23
11.	Roxithromycin	Broad spectrum semisynthetic macrolide antibiotic	To mask the bitter taste it is formulated as chewable tablet	Complexation technique	Indion-214, Amberlite IR P64, Carbopol 934P, Pearlitol, Spray dried lactose	Use of cation exchange resin offers good method for preparing taste masked substrates of Roxithromycin. Complexation of Roxithromycin with Amberlite IRP64 increases acceptability and palatability of formulated dispersible tablets	24
12.	Lamotrigine	Antiepileptic	To avoid difficulty in swallowing it is formulated as chewable tablet	Direct compression, wet granulation	Mannitol (Pearlitol 500DC),Mannitol (Pearlitol 200SD),Mannitol (Pearlitol 160C), Ludipress, Crospovidone, Povidone (PVP K	Wet granulation was good technique using the pearlitol 500 DC grade of mannitol for the formulation of chewable dispersible tablets	25

13.	Diclofenac sodium	Non steroidal anti inflammatory drug	To mask the taste of the drug	Microencapsulation with ethyl cellulose, Ethyl cellulose pan coating, inclusion complexation with cyclodextrin followed by coating with aqueous dispersion of ethyl cellulose	30), Magnesium stearate, Talc, Colloidal silica Ethyl cellulose, Cyclodextrin	Tablets with ethyl cellulose pan coating and inclusion complexation with cyclodextrin coated with ethyl cellulose aqueous dispersion showed fast release than microcapsules	26
14.	Ibuprofen	Non steroidal anti inflammatory drug	To mask the bitter taste it is formulated as chewable tablet	Coating drug with Ethyl cellulose, Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose, Eudragit E 100, Eudragit RD 100	Ethyl cellulose, Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose, Eudragit E 100, Eudragit RD 100, Mannitol, Sorbitol	Evaluation studies of the optimized formulation before and after stability studies showed no significant difference in drug content, drug release profiles, physicochemical and organoleptic properties	27
15.	Chlorpheniramine maleate	Antihistamine	To mask the taste it is formulated as chewable tablet	Spray drying	Pharmagum TM, Sucralose, Aerosil 200	The obtained results from the present experiment indicated that Pharmagum TM based formulation of Chlorpheniramine maleate had a positive outcome based on qualitative observations and quantitative measurement of different parameters	28
16.	Verapamil hydrochloride	Antihypertensive	To avoid difficulty in swallowing it is formulated as chewable tablet	Compressing beads coated with polymers	Hydroxyl propyl methyl cellulose, Polyethylene oxide, Ethyl cellulose, Lactose, Sodium starch glycolate	Controlled release properties of this new formulation do not change by chewing or crushing the tablet first. Such a tablet could be valuable for all patients including those who have difficulty in swallowing such as pediatrics and geriatrics	29
17.	Albendazole	Anthelmintic	To improve compliance in children it is formulated as chewable tablet	Aqueous granulation, Non aqueous granulation, Direct	Lactose monohydrate, Starch, Sodium starch glycolate, Isopropyl alcohol,	Tablets prepared by direct compression showed better dissolution rate when compared to tablets	30

				compression	Purified water, prepared by non Mannitol, Sodium aqueous granulation saccharide, and aqueous Carmofine color, granulation Pineapple flavor, Magnesium stearate, Talc, Aerosil		
18.	Carbamazepine	Antiepileptic	To mask the taste of the drug and avoid difficulty in swallowing	Solid dispersion by kneading method	β – cyclodextrin, 2-hydroxy propyl betacyclodextrin, orange flavor powder, spray dried mannitol, sodium starch glycolate, microcrystalline cellulose PH 102, magnesium stearate	Incorporation of cyclodextrins and hydroxyl propyl betacyclodextrin to the drug by kneading method gave acceptable dissolution results	31
19.	Albendazole	Anthelmintic	To avoid difficulty in swallowing	Wet granulation	Maize starch, Lactose, Microcrystalline cellulose, Povidone, Sodium lauryl sulphate, Sunset yellow supra, Sodium saccharin, Croscarmellose sodium, Sodium starch glycolate, Orange flavor, Pippermint flavor, Aerosil, Magnesium stearate	Formulation with 5% Croscarmellose sodium, 8% Sodium starch glycolate, 2% Sodium lauryl sulphate showed better drug release of 81.03% in 30min and satisfied all criteria for chewable tablets	32
20.	Loratidine	Non sedating antihistamine	For aesthetic appeal and ease of administration	Wet granulation	Microcrystalline cellulose(Avicel- Ph 101), Lactose Monohydrate, Mannitol (Pearlitol 25C), Ethyl cellulose (Ethocel Std 10FP), Guar gum, Povidone K-30, Maize starch, D&C Yellow No 10, D&C Red No 40, FD&C Yellow No 6, Citric acid, Raspberry flavor, Aspartame, Sodium starch glycolate, Colloidal Silica, Magnesium stearate	The formulation without use of ethyl cellulose and using Microcrystalline cellulose and guar gum showed 100% drug release in 60min and complies all the ideal characteristic of chewable tablets	33

List of Abbreviations:

API: Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient

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The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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